

A 1.4.1 Protocol for the comparison of mercury measurements in ambient air

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INTRODUCTION

Mercury (Hg) is a pollutant of particular interest that, given its chemical and physical properties and its ubiquitous presence in the environment, has combined qualities of toxicity and potential for bioaccumulation in aquatic and terrestrial biosystems. During the last decades the attention towards its monitoring has been constantly increased. A large number of activities have been carried out to characterize the levels of Hg species in ambient air and precipitation, to understand their variability over time and how they depend on physico-chemical parameters on temporal and spatial scale. The understanding of the pathways by which Hg is released into the atmosphere, transformed, deposited and eventually incorporated into biota is therefore of crucial importance to evaluate the impact on the environmental ecosystems. This thorough assessment necessarily passes through its accurate and precise quantification in a rigorous and internationally comparable way. In this direction were addressed the indications of the European Commission (EC) Fourth Air Quality Daughter Directive (4th DD)², which require all Member States to monitor total gaseous mercury (TGM) in ambient air, as well as nickel, arsenic and cadmium in the PM₁₀ particulate phase.

Following these directions, the EC commissioned the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) to produce a standard method for the measurement of TGM in ambient air, as it has been done for many other ambient pollutants. The resulting document, “EN 15852: 2010 Ambient air quality—Standard method for the determination of total gaseous mercury” has been officially adopted as the reference method for Member States in support of the European legislation (UNI EN 15852:2010). During the development of this method, CEN Working Group 25 (WG25), which was in charge of its realization, conducted a field trial study to assess the measurement uncertainty obtained by following the draft standard method, and more specifically the uncertainty variation with TGM concentration, at different locations (Brown et al. 2010). This study was the first attempt to evaluate the comparability of the results of TGM analysis obtained with commercially available instruments from different manufacturers, which were operating in parallel under the same experimental conditions.

The results showed that the main causes of variability in results depend on the experimental set up and calibration, rather than the type of instrument or the manufacturer. More strictly, calibration step resulted to be fundamental, and its effectiveness depends on a combination of the analyst's skill and the reliability of the calibrators.

The development of measurement systems traceable to International System of Units (SI) has been for years an objective of the EMPIR program of EURAMET and in the SI-Hg project part of the work is aimed at improving the

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performance of gas generators through the development of certification protocol for elemental and oxidized mercury gas generators used in the field traceable to SI (Task 1.1 and Task 2.3).

The protocol herein presented provides the operational guidance to carry out a comprehensive intercomparison of the measurement performance of different commercially available systems for Hg monitoring, each calibrated with different SI-traceable certified gas generators. Hg concentrations (elemental and/or oxidized) in ambient air obtained using instrumentation that potentially differs in model type, brand, and principle of operation will be considered, and the data collected will also provide information on the effect of the calibration strategy on the quality of the measurements. Besides the use of online instrumentation, passive samplers for Hg monitoring (PASs) will also be included in the intercomparison exercise, thus providing advances on the experimental uncertainty associated with their use.

MCU OBSERVATORY

The sampling site selected for the comparison exercise measurement is the Monte Curcio Climatic Environmental Observatory (MCU), located in a rural area within the Sila National Park in the Calabria region, southern Italy (39° 18'57.2" N 16° 25'23.6" E; 1780 m a.s.l.). This Observatory is a regional station of the Global Atmosphere Watch program (GAW) network, for the control of greenhouse gases, and is a master site of the Global Mercury Observation System (GMOS) network, for the monitoring of atmospheric mercury levels (Sprovieri et al. 2016; Dinoi et al. 2017; Sprovieri et al. 2017; Bencardino et al. 2019; Moretti et al. 2021). Due to its high-altitude, the station is a background site with a completely free horizon, thus allowing atmospheric monitoring measurements with large spatial representativeness. Furthermore, the absence of local contamination sources provides the advantage to potentially intercept long-range transported air masses, being also in a strategic position in the middle of the Mediterranean basin, 30 and 60 km far from the Tyrrhenian and the Ionian Sea, respectively (Figure 1). This choice is in accordance with the provisions of the reference method EN 15852: 2010 (E), which requires the selection of background stations as sites for the representativeness of a large geographical area.

The station is equipped with a wide variety of instruments for the monitoring of the air quality, e.g., greenhouse gas analyzers, atmospheric mercury analyzers, aerosol samplers, and meteorological sensors.

Given the low concentrations of TGM generally recorded at MCU (up to 2 ng m⁻³), the intercomparison exercise carried out under these conditions is of particular interest because it allows to evaluate the effectiveness of the involved instrumentations in their lower part of the linear dynamic range, i.e., in a concentration range where it is easier to have discordant results due to measurement uncertainties and instrumental bias.

FIGURE 1. MONTE CURCIO SAMPLING STATION (A) AND ITS GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION (B). PICTURE FROM (BENCARDINO ET AL. 2019).

As reported above, MCU site is part of the global network on mercury (GMOS) where mercury measurements are continuously performed following the standard operating procedures (SOPs) developed, established, and followed by all the monitoring stations of the network to harmonize and make comparable all observations coming out from the GMOS sites worldwide distributed. Harmonized networks using the same operational and data quality control standards are strongly recommended for field data collection in various regions of the world. GMOS represents a unique technological infrastructure oriented to archive, control quality, and share collected information in globally distributed monitoring stations. The network has stations located in different environmental scenarios, including sea level observatories, high altitude stations and polar areas (Sprovieri et al. 2016, 2017). The infrastructure gathers mercury measurements in near-real time from instruments, archives them as Level-0 product (raw data) and starts processing to control their quality through an automatic centralized system (G-DQM), based on SOPs, and leaving the site operator to confirm or reject the controlled data (D'Amore et al. 2015). After expert acceptance, data are archived as Level-1 product (Quality Controlled/Quality Assured data). Final actions include metadata production and data publication as web map services in compliance with the appropriate standards. GMOS is, in addition, recognized as the unique global monitoring network that contributes to the Global Observation System for Mercury (GOS4M) [www.gos4m.org] aimed to coordinate the global observation network for mercury in support of the Minamata Convention on Mercury (MCM). Therefore, the comparison exercise at MCU could provide a useful contribution to the GMOS network on mercury measurements. Improving the accuracy of existing instruments and developing new technologies (i.e., passive Hg samplers) for routinely measuring mercury is critically needed to provide high-quality data for further understanding the chemical forms and compounds of mercury in the air on global scale (Naccarato et al. 2020). Only through comparison of multiple calibrated measurements results can be determined to be accurate. Lack of calibration is currently a major shortcoming. In this context, the comparison exercise at MCU station using calibrated with SI-traceable certified gas generators is crucial, considering the limitations of sampling methods, their numerous artifacts, and environmental interferences that can affect them. The new information gathered from the intercomparison at MCU may be used to revisit and better explain certain features of previous data sets and measurement–model comparison performed in the recent past within the GMOS network. Ongoing high-quality measurements of atmospheric mercury will be key in evaluating the environmental benefit of regulation on behalf of the MCM.

COMPARISON EXERCISE

FEATURES OF THE SURVEYED Hg ANALYZERS

The comparison exercise will be carried out using commercially available instruments, also produced by different companies, along with the inclusion of passive sampling technologies.

The principle of operation of active analyzers can rely on the TGM trapping on absorption cartridges followed by thermal desorption and detection by atomic fluorescence spectrometry (AFS) or on the Hg detection by atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). Similarly, instruments that allow direct measurement in ambient air by AAS can also be included in the comparison. The instrumentation shall be capable of operating on 220V. If the participants in the comparison come from countries where the equipment works with a different voltage, it shall be necessary that they will be equipped with an appropriate voltage transformer. The used instrumentation shall be capable of being manually calibrated using at least one of the gas generators studied in Tasks 1.1 and Task 2.3 of SI-Hg project, and on which the traceable certification protocols have been developed.

Participants will be asked to join the campaign with their own measuring systems that are required for the intercomparison exercise and the availability of qualified personnel for their correct use. In the event that, due to force majeure, it is not possible the presence of qualified personnel specialized in the use of each type of analyzer operating during the intercomparison, the participants will be asked to provide to the staff present all the indications and instructions necessary for the proper use of the instrumentation. For each analytical system and generator involved, a summary diagram will be drawn up with all its operational features (e.g., flow, voltage, time resolution, interfaceability with PC, possible remote control).

In the case of PASs, these usually rely on the unassisted diffusion of Hg onto a sorbent material, without the use of external pumps, electric power, and carrier gas for their functioning. Thus, their operation entails the deployment to ambient air for fixed time periods, generally lasting from 2 to 12 weeks. At the end of this period, PASs are sealed and stored before the subsequent analysis. Possible candidates for the comparison exercise would be the PASs commercialized by Tekran Corporation, (i.e., the MerPAS[®] devices) which are currently in use at some monitoring sites in the GMOS network. They are radial-type samplers based on sulfur-impregnated activated carbon (HGR-AC) as sorbent material, housed within the popular White Radiello[®] diffusive body (McLagan et al. 2016). The analytical approach for Hg quantification entails the thermal desorption of the sorbent material and CV-AAS detection following the guidelines of US-EPA Method 7473, whence the amount of sorbed Hg is derived. Conversion of that value to a time-averaged Hg concentration is then accomplished by application of the first Fick's law (Eq 1):

$$C = \frac{m}{SR \cdot t} \quad (1)$$

Where C is the time-averaged concentration in ng m^{-3} , m is the blank-corrected amount in ng of sorbed Hg, t is the deployment time (days), and SR is the sampling rate ($\text{ng m}^{-3} \text{day}^{-1}$), which defines the amount of Hg collected from a certain volume of air per unit time.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND METHODOLOGY

All instruments will be placed inside the station, operating at an internal temperature of about 20°C which is regulated by an air-conditioned system. All analyzers will be connected to a common intake manifold with a constant internal temperature, which samples the ambient air from the top of the station at a height of about 8 meters above the ground. The sampling inlet will not be located in the immediate vicinity of any potential source of mercury pollution, thus enabling the most uniform and representative sampling. The sampling inlet is of PTFE material and is constructed so that rain or snow could not enter in the sampling system (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. INTAKE MANIFOLD FOR MULTIPLE SAMPLING INLETS FOR ONLINE INSTRUMENTATION.

The sampling lines shall be made of a material suitable to be used with the sampling inlet described above that is already available at the station. Preferably, they shall be made of material such as FEP or PTFE.

The analyzers will be placed into a rack cabinet with adjustable shelves or, if necessary, on physical laboratory benches.

In addition, meteorological data (i.e., temperature, relative humidity, pressure, wind speed and wind direction) will be also recorded continuously so that results could be recalculated to reference conditions (1013 hPa and 293 K) and expressed as a mass concentration in nanograms per cubic meter of air under reference conditions.

PASs will be deployed on metal support racks mounted at a height of about 2 meters above ground to ensure free air circulation. These racks will be placed close to the external inlet of the active instrumentation.

STUDY DESIGN

The field trial will consist in sampling of mercury in ambient air using 2-5 analyzers working in parallel. Each instrument will work in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, referring also to operational

documents such as Standard Operation Procedures (SOPs) developed by international organizations and research groups, provided that they have consolidated experience in the use of the involved instrumentation. The resolution at which each analyzer shall operate in terms of measured concentration will depend on its sensitivity and the ambient Hg concentrations. The length of the measurement period shall be selected in order to collect enough mercury to satisfy the quality control and uncertainty requirements of the EU15852:2010 standard. However, the measurement time shall not be so long that degradation of gold traps or sample breakthrough occurs.

Active Hg sampling will be supplemented by the exposure of passive samplers. Five PAS samplers will be deployed as replicates for (multiple) time periods, within a time frame of 2-12 weeks (e.g., deployments lasting 2, 4, 6, and 8 weeks). Furthermore, a field blank will be included in each round, in order to assess for potential contamination during sampler assembling, transport, deployment, retrieval and storage. All deployment and retrieval operations will be conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions.

CALIBRATION

The calibration of each active analyzer will be performed according to the manufacturer; as an alternative, linear regression model using n calibration points could be defined on the basis of the instrumental range of each analyzer, which, however, must be of the order of ng m^{-3} , so as to consider the typical concentration values recorded at Monte Curcio. Calibration will be performed manually at the station and will be followed by a measurement period, thus allowing the comparison of the measured concentrations and the calculation of the associated uncertainties. In addition, bias among calibrations performed with different gas generators could be assessed by feeding each analyzer with known Hg concentration using a homemade sampling inlet, consisting of a union Tee with a septum for syringe injection on one side, a connection to a zero-air generator on the other side and the connection to the Hg analyzer on the third side by means of Teflon tubing (de Krom et al. 2021).

The active instruments will be considered to be independent of each other, whether from the same or different manufacturers, for the purposes of data analysis. Since different instruments could provide data with different temporal resolution, the data produced by each analyzer will be averaged over a period of time, e.g., on an hourly or daily basis, in order to obtain comparable and reliable data.

Each average value will be considered valid and representative of the time frame if it results from at least 90% of the data that can be collected. Otherwise, the average values that do not respect this condition will not be considered in the data report and in the subsequent statistical analysis.

The comparison exercise shall be accommodated to the actual number of participants, the number of Hg generators and analyzers available, and the operating conditions present at the particular time when it is going to be conducted. Depending on these conditions, two different scenarios for undertaking the work can be hypothesized.

1. First scenario: Calibration by one gas generator

In the case only one certified generator will be available, all the instruments involved in the comparison will be calibrated in the field (i.e., directly at the station) manually with the same generator. The calibrations will be performed by feeding each analyzer with Hg calibration gas at a concentration level as close as possible to the concentrations expected during the measurement. This procedure will be repeated at fixed time intervals and will be followed each time by a period of measurement, for comparison purposes. The

Hg concentrations recorded during the different measurement periods will be treated by statistical data analysis. The analyzers involved will thus be evaluated based on a comparison of the recorded average Hg concentrations, but also considering the dispersion of the measurements in each sampling period. The collected data will also allow to assess the measurement uncertainty between the analyzers running in parallel, while reiterating the measurement periods will give information on the performance variation after the system on/off switch and re-calibration.

2. Second scenario: Calibration by two or more gas generators

In case more generators certified with the protocol developed in task 1.1 will be available, the effects of the calibration obtained with all generators will be evaluated. All the instruments involved in the comparison will be calibrated in the field (i.e., directly at the station) manually with one generator and then used in a measurement period to compare the results. Subsequently, calibration of the same instruments with the next generator will take place followed by another measurement period. The experimental scheme will be repeated until all available generators are used. This strategy will allow to evaluate the measurement uncertainty between the data collected by the analyzers also as a function of the calibrator used. For a more robust evaluation the experimental scheme proposed for each generator will be repeated in order to have also an estimate of the inter-day variability of the measurement uncertainty.

t=0

- mean mass concentrations γ_A, γ_B
- relative combined uncertainties u_A, u_B
- relative expanded uncertainty U_1

t=t₁

- mean mass concentrations γ_A, γ_B
- relative combined uncertainties u_A, u_B
- relative expanded uncertainty U_2

In the case where multiple generators certified with the protocol developed in Task 1.1 are available, it may also be possible to calibrate the analyzers involved with different generators before starting each sampling period. The choice of the generator to be used for each analyzer will be based on contingent experimental needs or on specific preferences indicated by the manufacturer and/or analyst for a particular type of generator. The calibrations will be periodic with a pre-determined time intervals and each will be followed by a measurement period for comparison purposes. The data collected will allow to assess the measurement uncertainty between the different analyzers running in parallel and also evaluate the trend of the measurements between different sampling periods over time.

Calibration of PASs involves estimating the sampling rate (SR, $\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$) often obtained through laboratory experiments involving exposure of PASs to known amounts of mercury (McLagan et al. 2018). SR is a fixed value that is also used in Eq 1 to derive the time-averaged Hg concentration after exposure in ambient air.

The level of uncertainty about the SR calculation and its propagation on the measurement result is still a field of study. It has been shown, for example, that the SR value can be affected by the meteorological exposure conditions of passive samplers (Naccarato et al. 2020). In addition, it has been shown that its calculation from field exposure differs from that derived under laboratory conditions.

An advance in this area will be made by including PASs in the intercomparison exercise and providing for calculation of SR and its uncertainty using concentrations from active analyzers calibrated with SI-certified generators.

PAS replicates will be deployed within a time frame of 2-12 weeks (e.g., deployments lasting 2, 4, 6, and 8 weeks) in parallel with the active analyzers calibrated with certified generators. Regression analysis between the average Hg concentrations from active sampling in each deployment period vs. the Hg masses from PASs will be used to derive an experimental SR (SR_{exp}), as the slope of the linear regression:

$$SR_{exp} = \frac{m}{C \cdot \Delta t}$$

The SR_{exp} will be compared with the currently available values. The results of the comparison will be disseminated to the scientific community in order to improve the accuracy of the Hg quantification, and the SR value will be used in the next monitoring campaigns at the Monte Curcio GMOS station.

DATA REPORTING AND EVALUATION

The raw concentration data obtained from the intercomparison exercise will be collected and exported to a template spreadsheet shared among participants, or equivalent program for processing the results. Their contents will be handled in accordance with the data management guidelines established by the project to obtain findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data (SI-Hg Data Management Plan). This template shall contain information about type of gas generator and analyzer, details on the instrumental parameters as flow and time resolution, the calibration level in terms of injected Hg mass, and the measured concentration on a predefined temporal basis. These latter values will be then compared each other, and their difference will be evaluated using statistical tools such as the t-test (ISO 2854), F-test (ISO 2854), analysis of variance (ANOVA- ISO 5725-2) and chi-squared test (ISO 2854) to assess the agreement between measurements in terms of statistically significant difference between the averages and the data variance.

More specifically, the t-test will be used to compare the average concentration values of the two data sets and determine if they came from the same population, while ANOVA will be used to compare the averages of more than two sets of concentration data. F-test will be used to study the variance of the datasets pointing out differences in measurement trends over time while chi-squared test will be used to test for independence between categorical variables in the intercomparison exercise, thus showing whether there is non-randomness in the variability of a data set.

In case of two or more explanatory factors (e.g. type of gas generator), variance partitioning analysis (VPA) coupled with linear mixed effect model could be used to quantify the proportion of variation in concentration that owes to each factor. The linear mixed effect model allows to predict the concentration value as a function of a single fixed effect (i.e., the model intercept, which should represent the overall mean concentration), and some random effects (i.e., the factors). Based on this model, then the variance partitioning analysis is used to identify whether two or more variables (within the context of mixed effect model results) are independent (i.e., orthogonal), or whether they explained some proportion of shared variation (non-independent)

In addition to the inferential analysis of the data, the performance of the analyzers will be compared by evaluating the uncertainty on the output concentrations of the calibrated analytical systems.

The theory underpinning the statistical evaluation of the field trial process will be the prosecution of that used previously by CEN/TC 264/ WG 14 'Heavy Metals'. This method used the assumption that the mean value yielded by several different types of instruments at different locations when measuring different concentration levels represents the best estimate of the 'true value' in ambient air. It is also assumed that the spread of these results is a good estimate of the uncertainty in the mean value.

Both the random and nonrandom contributions to the uncertainty are considered by the general form:

$$u_c(\gamma) = \sqrt{u_r^2(\gamma) + u_s^2(\gamma)}$$

where $u_c(\gamma)$ is the relative combined uncertainty in the TGM concentration in ambient air, and $u_r(\gamma)$ and $u_s(\gamma)$ are the relative random and non-random contributions, respectively, to this uncertainty.

Assuming that the field trial will consist of M instruments operating in parallel over N days and that the data produced by each instrument will be averaged to produce a daily mass concentration value $\gamma_{d,i}$ (that is on day d from sampler i), we can define the terms:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{d=1}^N \bar{\gamma}_d \quad \bar{\gamma}_d = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_{d,i}$$

$$\delta_{d,i} = \gamma_{d,i} - \bar{\gamma}_d$$
$$\bar{\delta}_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{d=1}^N \delta_{d,i} \quad \sigma_i = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{d=1}^N (\delta_{d,i} - \bar{\delta}_i)^2}{N - 1}}$$

where γ is the mean mass concentration over all N days and across all M instruments. $\gamma_{d,i}$ is the mean mass concentration measured by instrument i on day d . $\bar{\gamma}_d$ is the mean mass concentration on day d across all M instruments. $\delta_{d,i}$ is the absolute deviation of instrument i from the mean mass concentration on day d . $\bar{\delta}_i$ is the absolute mean deviation of instrument i from the mean mass concentration over all N days. σ_i is the standard deviation of the absolute deviation of instrument i over all N days. It follows that the random contribution to the relative combined uncertainty from instrument i is given by:

$$u_{r,i}(\gamma) = \frac{\sigma_i}{\gamma \sqrt{N}}$$

and that the non-random contribution to the relative combined uncertainty from instrument i is given by:

$$u_{s,i}(\gamma) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\bar{\delta}_i}{\gamma}\right)^2 + u_{i,\text{vol}}^2}$$

where $u_{i,\text{vol}}$ is the relative uncertainty in the sampled volume for instrument i —usually a standard uncertainty of approximately 3%. The relative combined uncertainty from instrument i is given by:

$$u_{c,i}(\gamma) = \sqrt{u_{r,i}^2(\gamma) + u_{s,i}^2(\gamma)}$$

and $u_c(\gamma)$, the relative combined uncertainty at each field trial location is then given by:

$$u_c(\gamma) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M u_{c,i}(\gamma)$$

The relative expanded uncertainty U is then calculated by using a coverage factor k , corresponding to a level of confidence of approximately 95%, thus:

$$U = k u_c(\gamma)$$

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Similarly, we may estimate the uncertainty in the daily average over all instruments on any day d , $u_{c,d}(\gamma)$, as the sum in quadrature of the average absolute relative deviation of all instruments on day d , the average random uncertainty exhibited by the set of instruments over all days, and the average uncertainty in flow, thus:

$$u_{c,d}(\gamma) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \delta_{d,i}}{\bar{\gamma}_d M}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^M u_{r,i}(\gamma)}{M}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^M u_{i,\text{vol}}^2}{M}\right)^2}$$

As will be shown this uncertainty is dominated by the first term, representing the daily non-random uncertainty. Similarly, the relative expanded uncertainty on a given day, U_d , is then calculated by using a coverage factor k , corresponding to a level of confidence of approximately 95%, thus:

$$U_d = k u_{c,d}(\gamma)$$

For the field trials in question the 95% level of confidence may be approximated by using $k=2$.

All the uncertainties obtained will be evaluated by means of inferential analysis, such as the F and Chi-square distributions/tests (under normality assumptions) for the squared standard uncertainties.

As concerns PASs, the uncertainty of SR_{exp} derived from the intercomparison exercise will be calculated using direct error propagation from the errors of the sorbed Hg amount and the uncertainty on the active Hg concentration. Furthermore, the SR_{exp} will be compared to the currently used SR which are provided by the manufacturer or available from literature, and any deviation or discrepancy will be assessed seeking for the statistical significance of results.

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